

Search for Potent Anti-viral Agents : Synthesis of 2-Phenyl-3-Benzimidazolyl-alkyl/arylalkyl 6-Bromo-Quinazolin (3H)-4-ones as Possible Anti-viral Agents

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Fifteen new 2-Phenyl-3-benzimidazolyl-alkyl/arylalkyl-6-bromo-quinazolin (3H)-4-ones were prepared and tested for antiviral activity against Vaccinia and Ranikhet viruses, but contrary to our expectations none of them was found to possess significant activity.

BENZIMIDAZOLES have been reported to be very active against different viruses¹⁻³. Quinazolones have been found to show diverse pharmacological activities mainly as C.N.S. depressants⁴⁻⁶ and recently have been reported as anti-virals⁷. As the presence of both the nuclei viz. Quinazolone and benzimidazole in a single compound might result in a potent anti-viral compound, we have synthesised 2-phenyl-3-benzimidazolyl-alkyl / arylalkyl-6-bromo-quinazolin(3H)-4-ones of type (I) by the condensation of 2-phenyl-3-carboxyalkyl/aryl-6-bromo-quinazolin (3H)-4-ones with substituted *o*-phenylene diamines and tested then for anti-viral activity.

- (a) Y = H, Z = H
 (b) Y = CH₃, Z = CH₃
 (c) Y = Cl, Z = H

Experimental

All the melting points are taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

(i) *5-Bromo-anthranilic acid*: This was prepared by the method of Wheeler and Oats⁸, m.p. (210-212°).

(ii) *6-Oxo-2-phenyl-4,5-(3'-bromobenzo)-1,3-oxazin*: This was prepared by the method of Sammour, Fahmy and Mahmoud⁹ m.p. (204-205°).

(iii) *6-Bromo-2-phenyl-3-carboxyalkyl/arylalkyl quinazolin (3H)-4-ones*: These were prepared by the method of Misra et al.¹⁰.

(iv) *2-Phenyl-3-benzimidazolyl-alkyl/arylalkyl-6-bromo-quinazolin (3H)-4-ones*:

These compounds were prepared by adopting the method of Pool, Harwood and Ralston¹¹. An equimolar (0.05 mole) mixture of 6-bromo-2-phenyl-3-carboxyalkyl/arylalkyl-quinazolin(3H)-4-ones and simple or substituted *o*-phenylenediamine was heated at its boiling point for 30 minutes in an oil bath. The products were isolated and recrystallized from dilute ethanol. The physical constants of the compounds are recorded in Table I.

Anti viral Screening: All the 15 compounds were tested for anti-viral activity against Ranikhet and Vaccinia viruses in a stationary culture of Chorio-allantoic membrane of chick embryo at a drug dilution of 0.05 mg/ml by HA test¹². The compounds used against the Ranikhet and Vaccinia Viruses were 0.064 HA/ml and 50 PFU/ml respectively. Contrary to our expectations none of the compounds showed significant anti-viral activity.

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TABLE-1

PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF 2-PHENYL-3-BENZIMIDAZOLYL ALKYL/ARALKYL 6-BROMO QUINAZOLIN (3H)-4-ONES OF TYPE I.

Sl. No.	X	Y	Z	M.P.°C	% Yield	Mol formular	% N																
							Found	Calc.															
*1.	-CH ₂ -	H	H	155	55	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ N ₄ OBr	13.24	13.31															
2.	-CH ₂ -	CH ₃	CH ₃	165	75	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ OBr	12.70	12.20															
3.	-CH ₂ -	Cl	H	175	60	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₄ OClBr	12.50	12.08															
4.	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	H	H	170	50	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₄ OBr	12.60	12.58															
*5.	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	CH ₃	CH ₃	190	80	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₄ OBr	11.38	11.88															
6.	-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	Cl	H	260	75	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ OClBr	12.56	12.07															
7.	CH-(CH ₃) ₂	H	H	180	65	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₄ OBr	13.32	11.83															
8.	CH-(CH ₃) ₂	CH ₃	CH ₃	165	58	C ₂₇ H ₂₅ N ₄ OBr	11.66	11.17															
9.	CH-(CH ₃) ₂	Cl	H	156	60	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₄ OClBr	11.60	11.30															
10.	CH ₂ -CH(CH ₃) ₂	H	H	230	70	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ OBr	11.54	11.48															
11.	CH ₂ -CH(CH ₃) ₂	CH ₃	CH ₃	210	72	C ₂₈ H ₂₇ N ₄ OBr	10.64	10.87															
12.	CH ₂ -CH(CH ₃) ₂	Cl	H	190	80	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ OClBr	11.22	10.73															
13.	CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	H	H	160	78	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ N ₄ OBr	11.24	10.76															
*14.	CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	CH ₃	125	60	C ₃₁ H ₂₅ N ₄ OBr	9.70	10.20															
15.	CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	Cl	H	130	55	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ N ₄ OClBr	10.60	10.08															
							Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.									
*(1)%C							59.00	59.47	%H	3.32	3.65	(5) %C	63.41	63.53	%H	4.00	4.44	(14) %C	53.78	53.81	%H	4.40	4.55

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